

Ministry of Health of the Republic of Moldova

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FACULTY OF MEDICINE II

Department of **Rheumatology and Nephrology**

Graduation Thesis

**BEHCETS DISEASE - CONTEMPORARY
ETIOPATHOGENETIC EXPLANATIONS, CURRENT
DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT POSSIBILITIES.**

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Chisinau, 2025

DECLARATION

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

BD	Bahcet's disease
As	Ankylosing spondylitis
GWAS	Genome-wide association studies
MHC	Major histocompatibility complex
HLA	Human Leukocyte Antigen
NK	Natural killer
GCS	Glucocorticoids
EULAR	European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology
ICBD	International Criteria for Behçet's Disease
RCT	Randomized controlled trial rct
CsA	Cyclosporine
PDE4	Phosphodiesterase-4
AZA	Azathioprine
INF	Anfliximab
ADA	Adalimumab
CYC	Cyclophosphamide
TNF	Tumor necrosis factor
HSV	Herpes simplex virus
CMV	Cytomegalovirus
DVT	Deep vein thrombosis
TB	Tuberculosis
SLE	Systemic lupus erythematosus
IBD	Inflammatory bowel disease

INTRODUCTION

Behçet's disease is an inflammatory, was first given its name in 1930 when it was described as an inflammatory, multisystemic, chronic disease with a relatively high recurrence rate, which had periodic flares, with each flare known as an exacerbation. Due to the many symptoms exhibited by patients, this disorder has more and more attention due to the potential important morbidities and prognostic impact on a patient's quality of life.[90] According to Hulusi Behçet (1937), this disorder has recurrent episodes of acute painful mucosal ulcers which are common within the mouth and the genitalia and may be accompanied by eye inflammation such in the case of uveitis. Patients suffering from this condition suffer qualitative life and productivity issues alongside suffering significant levels of morbidity as the condition is characterized by periods of remission and relapse [21].

The causes of Behçet's disease are still undetermined for the people; albeit it is assumed that there is a combination of both genetic predispositions and environmental factors. We should note the presence of the HLA-B51 allele that has been strongly associated with this disease suggesting a genetic component that predisposes individuals to BD. Aside from that, a multitude of genes as well as other environmental triggers may also be critical in inducing the disease in those with the right genetic background [56].

Diagnosing Behçet's disease is very challenging because of its variable clinical presentation and the lack of specific laboratory tests. Diagnosis is first posited on clinical criteria which includes recurrent oral ulcers in conjunction with some system manifestations [7]. This complex disease needs a multidisciplinary approach for good management, including specialists such as rheumatologists, ophthalmologists, and dermatologists.

Behçet's disease treatment options were designed to relieve the inflammation of the affected areas and to prevent further complications through immunosuppressive therapies. Typically, both corticosteroids and a few biological agents are used in the treatment of Behçet disease. Although we know widely about its [sic] clinical features and treatment modalities, we are still in the dark about the pathophysiology of this disease and the best management tactics [49].

We have learned much about Behçet's syndrome in the past two decades because of several discoveries, and now we know it is primary systemic vasculitis that strikes the blood vessels, large and small, alike [45] Contemporary scientific studies which bring forth new light on the subject such as the analyses of the biology of the perturbed immune system are the major cause of the disorder's shifting categorizations. These studies have identified significant genetic factors in the genomewide association research and new DNA sequencing

technologies [13].

In this review, we look at the most current and pertinent findings about the pathophysiology, clinical manifestation, and epidemiology of Behçet's illness. We additionally talk about the differential diagnosis and new specific therapies.

Aim of the study: To explore the contemporary etiopathogenetic explanations of Behçet's disease, primarily focusing on the interplay of various etiology which contribute to the onset and progression of the disease

Objectives:

1. To Review Etiopathogenesis:
2. To Analyze Clinical Presentation:
3. To Evaluate Diagnostic Criteria:
4. To Explore Treatment Strategies:
5. To Emphasize Multidisciplinary Management:
6. To Identify Future Directions:

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To attain the aim of the study, a literature analysis was conducted. The selection criteria were as follows:

Inclusion criteria:

1. Database: PubMed, Medline, Medscape, google scholar, Web of science
2. Type of articles: literature synthesis, meta-analysis, cross-sectional studies and case reports.
3. Keywords: “Behçet's disease”, “neurobehcet”, “HLA B51”, “pathergy test”, “vasculitis”
4. Studies were published in the last 10 years

Exclusion criteria:

1. Articles which were published not more than 10 years ago
2. Studies which were published in languages other than English were not taken.
3. Translational studies were also not taken.

1 BACKGROUND OF BAHCET'S DISEASE

1.1 Bahcets's disease

Behcet's disease (syndrome) is a systemic vasculitis with an unknown etiology which is characterized by damage to vessels of any type and caliber has clinically manifested by relapses of the ulcerative process in the oral cavity and genitals, damage to the eyes, joints, gastrointestinal tract (GIT), central nervous system (CNS) and other organs. It has a chronic course with truly unpredictable exacerbations and remissions and heterogeneity in demographic characteristics, the nature of organ damage, the frequency and severity of relapses, the course of the disease, response to treatment and prognosis[94] .

Reports of patients with clinical manifestations that are today attributed to BD can be found in the works of Hippocrates and old doctors of Japan, China and Arab countries, which shows that this disease there since ancient era. Some observations in patients with recurrent hypopyon and aphthous stomatitis are presented in the medical literature of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, a combination of individual signs of the disease are presented in the works of L. Blüthe (1908), H. Planner and F.Romenowsky (1940). Nevertheless, the disease was recognized long ago, most often, when touching on the history of its study, reference is made to the works of two researchers. When we are known about the ophthalmologist Benedict Adamantiades (B. Adamantiades), who was born in 1875 in the city of Prouse, in Asia Minor (now Bursa, Turkey), studied in Istanbul, and received his medical education at the University of Athens. In 1930, at the annual meeting of the Medical Society of Athens, B. Adamantiades presented a 20-year-old patient with recurrent iritis and hypopyon. In addition to the presentation of ophthalmological symptoms, this patient had aphthae in the mouth and genital area, pyoderma and arthritis. In 1946, the author described thrombophlebitis of peripheral vessels as a component of this disease.

Hulûsi Behçet, He was born in 1889 in Istanbul. He studied medicine and dermatology at the Gülhane Military Academy (Turkey), then in Budapest and Berlin.

Behcet's attention towards BD was a "three-symptom complex" dates back to 1920. A second patient with similar symptoms was described in 1930, and a third in 1937. In 1937, these cases were published in the international journal "Dermatologische Wochenschr". In coming years, H. Behcet reported on five more patients who, in addition to the three main symptoms, also had also have some signs of the disease called erythema nodosum, acneiform rashes and arthralgia. In 1941, ophthalmologist T. Jensen was the first to suggest to call it as "Behcet's syndrome". In 1947, at the International Congress of Dermatologists in Geneva, the "Three-symptom complex" was accepted this and nomenclature this disease "morbus Behçet's"

(Behcet's disease).

In recent years, many experts have proposed replacing the term BD with "Behcet's syndrome", because the exact meaning of "syndrome" more accurately reflects the essence of the disease, which is a kind of numerous symptoms. Geographical differences in the severity of the disease, the frequency of individual symptoms, familial aggregation of some of them, and how it works on drugs, especially cytokine inhibitors, and in variety clinical manifestations support this. The advocates of "Behcet's syndrome" support their view by the fact that there is no single diagnostic procedure or known common etiology to date, and until one exists, this set of symptoms should be considered a syndrome [31].

An alternative view is that there are enough common features for the condition to be considered a disease [37],[91].

1.2 Epidemiology and prevalence

The frequency of BD varies significantly in different geographic areas. Countries located along the eastern coast of the Mediterranean Sea and regions of Central and East Asia are endemic for BD. The location of these countries along the Great Silk Road and the association of the disease with a certain immunogenetic marker support the hypothesis that BD was spread by migration of nomadic tribes. The transfer of genetic material, along with exogenous agents, are considered factors responsible for the expansion of BD [70]. (Figure 1).

The map highlights regions where BD prevalence is highest.

Figure. 1. Prevalence of Behcet's disease [95]

The prevalence of BD varies between countries also between a variety of ethnic populations living in the same country. The Epidemiological studies that was performed along many

countries around the world have depicted very variable estimates of the prevalence of this disease vary, ranging from 0.1 per 100,000 in Hawaii to 664 people per 100,000 population in Northern Jordan. Coming to the overall prevalence of BD is 10.3 per 100,000 population worldwide. The disease has his highest prevalence in Turkey (80-600 per 100,000), Iran and Iraq (17-80 per 100,000), Korea (26.7-35.7 per 100,000), Japan (16 people per 100,000), China (14 per 100,000 population). While in Europe, the prevalence of the BD averages 2.1 - 5.3 per 100 thousand population, in North America/Caribbean Islands - 3.8 per 100 thousand [61]. It is known that in Russia BD is most often found among natives of the North Caucasus and Transcaucasia. Considering that the prevalence of BD in Russia does not exceed 10 cases per 100 thousand population [96].

Table 1 presents data on the prevalence of BD in some regions of the world [61, 96],[93],.

Region	Prevalence Rate per 100,000 Inhabitant
Turkey	20-420
Iran	80–100
Northern Europe	0.3–4.9
Sweden	2.3–4.9
Germany	0.3–4.87
England	0.27–0.6
Sothern Europe	1.5–15.9
Japan	16
Korea	26.7-35.7
China	14
Northern Jordan	664

It is very clear to say that BD is more common among people living between 30° and 45° north latitude compared to those living in Northern Europe [14]. The above data suggests that the Great Silk Road passed through certain regions of the Caucasus, especially nearby Turkey, where BD is dispersed [61].

1.3 Etiopathogenesis of Behçet's disease

1.3.1 Genetic susceptibility

The main signs of genetic influence and a complicated inheritance model of disease are increased incidence of diseases along the historic "Silk Road," familial aggregation, and relationship with genes both inside and outside the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) area [56], [62]. The main genetic susceptibility factor for BD is located inside the MHC class I region including the Human Leukocyte Antigen-B51 (HLA-B51). While we analysing the comparison those people with the HLA-B51/B5 allele to those without, the odds ratio for developing BD was 5.78 [62].

The Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have found and shown the role of many single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the etiopathogenesis of various diseases, including BD[34]. Normaly the gene polymorphisms that linked to BD seen in the molecules that react to microbes, and in genes that encode adhesion molecules and cytokines. The role of the cytokines may be impacted by polymorphisms in the genes that encode them, and these variations may also be linked to a higher risk of disease [43]. ERAP1, IL23 receptor (IL23R), IL-23R/IL-12RB2, IL-10, and STAT genes are among the non-HLA genetic correlations that researchers discovered using GWAS [40] .

Some abnormality in ERAP1, which is the gene coding the enzyme slicing the peptides for immune system presentation, is likely why certain mutations are common causes of psoriasis and ankylosing spondylitis[25]. They represent mutations that are linked to the diseases, such as psoriasis and ankylosing spondylitis, and alter the protein function. An experiment, interesting in the extreme, describing the fact that in interaction the same genetic variations that raise the risk for BD also seem to give protection against AS and psoriasis [13] has been conducted recently [84].

The contribution of ERAP1 polymorphisms in HLA-B51 patient is really significant, which is a gene mutation that directly belongs to the illness. The ERAP1 rs17482078 variation that is a p.Arg725Gln (p.Arg725Gln) gene, for example, might change how peptides bind to HLA-B51, thus affecting T-lymphocytes and natural killer (NK) cells' recognition of the immune response. This altered immune response could enhance the disease's progression. ER stress and protein misfolding, are the major factors for the initiation of inflammation. The same processes lead to misfolding of proteins in AS patients with HLA-B27; however, this theory has not been fully studied in BD patients. The intermediary pathways between BD and the process regarding this process may lead to BD pathology [30].

Another example is BD with the changes in the TNF promoter region. The raised inflammatory activity could happen due to variations in the expression of TNF, which are

related to gene polymorphisms [1], Persons with BD were more likely to show polymorphic versions of genes, and the increased production was associated with TNF in monocytes or mononuclear cells. Further BD risk factors could be the mutations in the Mediterranean fever gene [77].

1.3.2 Infection

Some research proposed that infection has a crucial role in triggering the BD. Virus such as HSV-1 and bacteria belongs to streptococcus that is the streptococcus sanguinis is suspected to have high homology with human proteins such as heat-shock proteins (HSP) and the cross-reaction leads to an immune response in genetically predisposed individuals [9] 9. Hulusi Behçet is the one authors firstly said regarding the disease has chance to relate an infectious agent. Variety of projects has been implemented to get investigated the association between HSV-1 and BD. Studd et al. in an situ DNA-RNA hybridization method, detected there is high chance of hybridization between HSV-1 DNA and complementary RNA in mononuclear cells of BD patient with healthy one[52].

There is a certain portion of strain are exclusively linked to BD. Evidence shows antibodies against this *S. sanguinis* and *S. pyogenes* are got from BD patients. Streptococcal 65-kDa HSP from very uncommon serotype (KTH-1, strain BD113-20) of oral *S. sanguinis* has been addressed an notable cause for the pathogenesis [15]. Also, IgM in BD patient can react with streptococcal α -enolase and glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase [97]. There are higher levels of Streptococci nis seen in oral mucosa of BD patients. And the *S. sanguinis* strain able to induce the secretion of inflammatory cytokines by the KTH-1 cells. [48]

Currently there are no reports show the association of *Borrelia burgdorferi* and or *Helicobacter pylori* in BD patients. But CMV, EBV, Parvovirus B19, Varicella zoster virus, Hepatitis virus also a possible chance of triggering [76].

1.3.3 Immunological mechanisms

Innate immunity of our body in response to the pathogenesis of BD. Triggers induced by microbes in our body are taken by our innate immunity via pathogen-related and/or danger-associated molecular patterns. Our body produce an excess number of cytokines such as macrophages and dendritic cells cause an increased producton of adaptive Th1- and Th17-related cytokines. First stages of BD in their results shows excessive amount of neutrophils an immunoregulatory group of innante immunity. NK cells are also some times seen [19]. There are some different mechanism shows the disorder in the innate immune response system is the increased formation of neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs). These traps allow neutrophils to

destroy extracellular pathogens with minimal damage to host cells. The main components of neutrophil extracellular traps are histones, enzymes and granule peptides (neutrophil elastase, myeloperoxidase, cathepsin G, lactoferrin, gelatinase, lysozyme C, calprotectin and others). The process of NETs formation is called NETosis and can be caused by various inducers: microorganisms, bacterial components, activated platelets, complementary peptides, autoantibodies, IL-8, monurate crystals, cigarette smoke. programmed neutrophil death is called as NETosis. This physiological mechanism can be potentially altered and hyperactivated in some autoimmune diseases, in particular in small vessel vasculitis, maintaining inflammation and leading to vascular damage. It has been shown that circulating neutrophils from patients with BD tend to secrete NETs in vitro and express higher levels of the cytoplasmic deiminase PAD4, and the use of colchicine and dexamethasone in these patients allows inhibition of spontaneous NETs formation by neutrophils [74], [46]

$\gamma\delta$ T lymphocytes are a minor population of T lymphocytes (1-10% of peripheral blood T cells) that express T cell receptors (TCRs) composed of γ and δ heterodimers. $\gamma\delta$ T lymphocytes play an important role in innate immunity as a first line of defense against microorganisms, in tumor control, and possibly in the modulation of autoimmune reactions. Polyclonal activation of peripheral blood $\gamma\delta$ T lymphocytes is characteristic of patients with BD. $\gamma\delta$ T lymphocytes in patients with exacerbation of BD more actively express CD29 and CD69, as well as IFN- γ and TNF- α . The significant local presence of $\gamma\delta$ T lymphocytes in active inflammatory foci in BD, characterized by increased expression of HSP60, suggests possible interactions between HSP and $\gamma\delta$ T lymphocytes [36]. It has been shown that V γ 9V δ 2+ T lymphocytes actively express TNF II and β 1 IL-12 receptors in exacerbation of BD, and infliximab (INF), a monoclonal antibody to TNF- α , inhibits activated V γ 9V δ 2+ T lymphocytes. $\gamma\delta$ T lymphocytes have also been shown to produce IL-17 as a proinflammatory early activator of neutrophils [29].

Also, some cytotoxic lymphocytes involved in the execution of the innate immune response. When the BD exacerbated, a large number of lymphocytes is noted. Some studies have shown that NK cells of patients with BD are disunite in response to Th1 and they secrete higher levels of TNF- α , IFN- γ and IL-2 during disease relapses [98].

BD is characterized by activation of T-lymphocytes both in the peripheral blood and in tissues. Similar to other autoimmune disorders and vasculitis, hyperproduction of Th1-type cytokines predominant in patients with BD. The concentration of both CD4+ and CD8+ T-lymphocytes producing proinflammatory Th1-type cytokines IL-2, 8, 12, 18, TNF- α and IFN- γ , as well as the level of these proinflammatory cytokines in the blood of patients with BD, are usually increased and correlate with disease activity. With damage to the gastrointestinal tract and skin manifestations of BD, an increase in the level of IL-12 and IL-23 in damaged tissues

[85].

BD vasculitis is classified under variable vasculitis by Chapel Hill in 2012 [45]. Which says there is an atypical nature of the histological and clinical manifestations of this disease. It includes 1) the same probability of affecting arteries and veins of all calibers (in general, veins are affected more often); 2) no increased risk of developing atherosclerosis compared to other inflammatory vascular diseases; 3) a unique tendency to form aneurysms, in particular in the pulmonary artery; 4) the absence of granulomatous inflammatory damage in the vessel wall. In BD there is no disturbance in coagulation cascade suggesting the formation thrombi. BD infiltrates, the vessels in BD mainly consist of neutrophils and lymphocytes. Unlike other systemic vasculitis, these cells in BD are localized more around the vessels than inside the wall. This histological perivascular infiltration in BB, has been demonstrated in lesions of the mucous membranes and eyes, as well as in pulmonary artery aneurysms⁶⁶. The pathogenesis of thrombotic manifestations of BD was shown that as a result of oxidative stress and excessive generation of active oxygen metabolites by neutrophils, post-translational modification of fibrinogen (carbonylation) occurs and the susceptibility of fibrin to plasmin lysis decreases. These results partially explain the positive effect of immunosuppressive, rather than anticoagulant therapy on thrombus formation in patients with BD [23].

1.4 Clinical manifestation of Behçet's disease

1.4.1 Mucocutaneous involvement

Mucocutaneous lesions are a very prominent in behçet's disease, which is most common and the first most manifestations[90]. They were seen equally in both genders, and include different types of skin and mucosal lesions, such as oral and genital ulcers, papulopustular lesions and nodular lesions[9]

1.4.1.1 Oral ulcer

Oral ulcers are seen in 95% of the patients, usually has more or long-lasting disease manifestation. Small oral ulcerations are mainly shown on the lips, the gingiva, the cheeks and the tongue, which usually disappear in 3–4 days, without any remnants or scar[81]. Fatigue, stress, histamine-rich or -liberating food, and stopping smoking have been found as chance that trigger the development of oral ulcers[89], while in female patients the trigger of oral ulcers has been found during menstruation[99]

Figure 2: Oral ulcers in patients with Behçet's disease: (A) left ventral side of tongue A centimeter aphthous lesion (B) main deep aphthae on both sides of the tongue; and (C) aphthous lesions with a herpetiform distribution on the ventral side of the tongue [100].

1.4.1.2 Genital ulcer

Genital ulcers that are seen in the scrotum part of men or in the major and minor labia in women are reported by 80–90% of bahcet's disease[81], and are the most seen manifestation of bahcet's disease. These lesions usually heal within 10–30 days, with formation of scars. [81]Unlike oral ulcers, genital ulcers tend to occur only in the early years following disease onset, and tend to disappear during the later course of the disease.

Acne-like or papulopustular lesions are seen on the face, upper chest, neck, shoulders and extremities which are seen around 85% of the patients, and they are normally 'benign', quick healing within 2–3 days without markings. Different from ulcers, papulopustular lesions are mostly found in the age of 50 or after[81]. Erythema nodosum is less seen as compared with the other mucocutaneous manifestations. It mostly affects the women, and mostly involves the extremities, with healing period of 7–10 days with hyperpigmentation that's marked as a consequence of this [81]. Despite relatively mild clinical severity, these symptoms have a substantial effect on patients' quality of life [27, 79]and, crucially, can coexist with considerable organ involvement [81]. When no other organs are affected, mucocutaneous symptoms are seen in around one-third of BD patients [8, 54]. Nonetheless, it has been determined that a higher incidence of mucocutaneous symptoms, notably oral ulcers, early in the course of the illness is a predictor of the emergence of major organ involvement, especially in male patients [101].

Figure 3: A painful deep ulcer over the left labia minora in acute [92].

1.4.2 Ocular involvements

Ocular problems noted around half of BD patients, with more incidence rate in males, most probably in the end of his third decade of life, also in the first 2 years after diagnosis[54],[33],[86]. The most seen eye manifestation is non-granulomatous posterior or panuveitis (which is usually bilateral), characterized by periods of exacerbation followed by remission. Isolated anterior uveitis is least reported and affects mainly women (5–10%). Retinal vasculitis is co-found in around 50% of cases. The most common complications of BD-related refractory eye involvement are cataracts, glaucoma and phthisis bulbi, which leads to worst scenario of loss of visual acuity in around 15–20% of cases. Bad visual prognosis is particularly more in patients with more than three ocular attacks in a year, strong vitreous opacity, and exudates within the retinal vascular arcade [2].

Figure 4: Bilateral Hypopyon [66].

1.4.3 Vascular complications

Vascular manifestations is a major clinical feature of BD. BD is classified, together with Cogan's syndrome, as a 'variable vessel' vasculitis, thus underlining its peculiar and atypical histological and clinical features[45]. While comparing to other systemic vasculitides, BD is characterized by the involvement of both arteries and veins of all sizes together at same time and shows an unique chance for the formation of aneurysm [45],[11]. In BD, a specific group of patients vulnerable for recurrent inflammatory thromboses involving the venous and, more rarely, the arterial vasculature, is called the 'vascular cluster' or 'angio-Behcet's' has been seen [91].

Vascular problems seen up to 40% of BD patients, with a higher number of existing cases in males [26], and they commonly represent an early disease manifestation [5]. Superficial venous thrombosis and deep vein thrombosis (DVT) are the most commonly seen vascular manifestations, concurrently affecting 15–40% of BD patients, and later they leading to post-thrombotic syndrome in the aggravated cases [67]. Venous thrombotic events in BD mostly shown in the superior or the inferior limbs, even though thrombosis of atypical sites (such as inferior and superior vena cava, hepatic veins with Budd–Chiari syndrome, portal vein, cerebral venous sinus and right ventricle) is a relevant and super specific clinical feature of BD [78].

Arterial involvement, even if far less common than venous disease, and considered as a significant vascular feature of BD, it's the one and chronic inflammatory diseases which can cause aneurysms that can affect peripheral, visceral and pulmonary arteries [11, 23]. Venous thrombosis is very frequently detected among the patients with aneurysms or pseudoaneurysms. Approximately 80% of patients showing pulmonary arterial involvement have been observed to also present with concurrent venous thrombosis, predominantly deep vein thrombosis (DVT). This correlation shows that the pathological mechanisms affecting both the venous and arterial systems of the vascular network may share similarities [72]. The simultaneous presence of arterial pulmonary aneurysms and peripheral venous thrombosis is characteristic of Hughes–Stovin syndrome, which some researchers currently regard as a clinical variant of 'angio-Behcet's'[18],[50]. The vascular complications associated with Behcet's syndrome significantly influence morbidity and long-term mortality rates.[20, 72].

1.4.4 Neurological manifestations

Neurological involvement occurs in nearly 5% of patients with Behcet's syndrome, with a higher number in males. Parenchymal neurological manifestations, referred to as 'neuro-Behcet's,' account for about 80–90% of all neurological cases, while the remaining instances are associated with cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST), which falls under the previously

mentioned vascular phenotype [75]. Different from other manifestations of the disease, parenchymal neurological issues usually arise later in the disease progression on an averaging around 5 years from the initial start of Behçet's syndrome[69]. These parenchymal manifestations mostly affect the brainstem, the junction of the telencephalon and diencephalon, and the basal ganglia, with spinal cord involvement is not that much seen; both the cerebral cortex and cerebellum are generally not affected from BD [51]. The most prevalent symptoms include a subacute (or, in rare cases, acute) onset of severe headaches, cranial nerve palsies, dysarthria, ataxia, and hemiparesis[69]. It is important to point that neurological symptoms and signs in Behçet's syndrome patients are not exclusively linked to neuro-Behçet's and may also come from conditions such as migraines or as side effects of treatment[47].

Magnetic resonance imaging is need for examination for differential diagnosis, and to find of large and extensive lesions and isolated brainstem atrophy is which is very specific for BD[47, 60]. On cerebrospinal fluid examination, pleocytosis and increased levels of protein can be found, but the positive result for oligoclonal bands is very rare [35]. Till now only a few biomarkers to distinguish BD and multiple sclerosis have been reported[5].

All together the vascular involvement and parenchymal neurological manifestations are the leading cause of BD related mortality, with death or loss of independence found 25–60% of patients [75]. The presence of pre-existing disabilities or dependencies, a primary or secondary progressive disease course, relapses occurring during the tapering of steroid doses, fever, meningeal signs, and bladder involvement are prognostic indicators linked to unfavorable outcomes in neuro-Behçet's disease [41].

1.4.5 Gastrointestinal manifestations

Gastric involvement is not as much as frequent attacks of BD, it meagerly around 5% of BD patients, which is equal in both genders. But geographic differences are reported, having the highest prevalence being depicted in the Far East [82]. In 5-10 days after the onset of oral ulcer gastric problems are reported. even more rarely it can also start before the first symptom of any other BD disease manifestation. The manifestations range from mild abdominal discomfort to severe pain. Severe complications like hemorrhage or perforation can also occur in emergency situations [44]. Lesions which focused in the terminal ileocecal region (almost 95% of cases), and less common the perianal and rectal area. gastrointestinal involvement shows so many similarities with Crohn's disease and with intestinal tuberculosis. We can differentiate this by endoscopic examination, that shows finding of round or oval ulcers of >1 cm of size, and/or punched-out lesions with very clear margins indicates BD-related involvement. Yet aphthous lesions are usually absent, and at histopathological examination non-specific neutrophilic or

lymphocytic phlebitis can be found [102]. While the associated mortality is minimal, the primary issue with gastrointestinal involvement in BD is the high rate of surgical intervention, which is needed in about 20% of cases at one year and in up to 50% of cases at ten years after diagnosis [31].

1.4.6 Clinical case of Bahcet's disease

Patient Details:

First name: Patient X,

Age: 35 years old

Gender: male

Present Complaints:

Patient came to the hospital Moderate knee arthralgia with decreased visual and having photosensitivity with uveitis (4-5 episodes/year), sometimes associated with oral ulcers

Disease History -:

He himself says that he is sick since 2019 with inflammatory pain in the knee joint After 1 week – eye pain, conjunctival hyperemia, photosensitivity, decreased visual acuity were present. He was admitted to the Ophthalmology department, with diagnosis of Acute panuveitis and treated with topical treatment with sol. Ketorolac, retrobulbar injections with sol. Betameson, with improvement. He was consulted by a rheumatologist, and diagnosed as undifferentiated seronegative spondylarthritis, oligoarthritic, uveitis, oral ulcers and treated with Sulfasalazine 500mg tab. 2 tab. 2 times/day was recommended. Being on treatment, the patient continues to complain of 4-5 episodes of exacerbation of uveitis per year. He is seeing a rheumatologist again in November 2020, and it is recommended to investigate urinary tract infections and intestinal infections and repeted consultation rheumatologist again 09.2021. At the time he was checked for sexually transmiited disease and HLA B27 antigen and found negative. In November 2021, the patient goes to Turkey, on a visit, an exacerbation of uveitis occurs. He consulted an ophthalmologist and prescribed with tab. Azathioprine 150mg/day, tab. Prednisolone 5mg/day. During 2022-2024, the patient suffers 4-5 exacerbations of uveitis per year, sometimes associated with oral ulcers. Each time, he is admitted to the Ophthalmology department, where he is administered topical NSAIDs, retrobulbar injections with GCS, with improvement. Since March 2024, the general condition worsens, arthralgias intensify, and visual acuity suddenly decreases. The patient administers this treatment for 2 months, in the meantime, suffers another exacerbation of uveitis, later abandons the background treatment, returning to tab. Sulfasalazine 500mg 2 tab 2 times/day. În aprilie 2024, se adresează repetat la reumatolog. In April 2024, he/she is referred to the rheumatologist again and recommended to

perform an CBC + ESR, biochemistry, HLA-B27, Anti-CCP antibodies, pelvic bone radiography, skeletal scintigraphy. Everything seems normal with Anti-CCP antibodies, HLA-B27 are negative. But on pelvic bone radiography he was diagnosed with Grade I coxarthrosis on the left. Repeated consultation with rheumatologist 17.05.2024 and diagnosed as undifferentiated seronegative spondyloarthritis, HLA B27 negative, arthritis (in atecedent), enthesitis (achylo-dinitis), recurrent uveitis. Because HLA B27 was negative, the lack of sacroiliitis, as well as an inadequate response to previous treatments, doctor scheduled for reevaluation In the Rheumatology hospital. In June 2024, the patient goes to Cyprus for a visit, where he suffers another exacerbation of uveitis, goes to the ophthalmologist, who refers him to a rheumatologis and suspected Behçet's disease, he indicated tests ENA-blot, HLA B27, HLA B51, pathergy test are indicated and found that HLA B51 and pathergy are positive. According to the ICBD criteria (2014), ≥ 4 points. Now he is diagnosed with bahcet's .It is recommended to initiate therapy with Azathioprine tab., Prednisolone tab. The patient refuses, returns to the Republic of Moldova. On September 2024, there has been a sudden decrease in visual acuity. The patient is referred to a private ophthalmological center. On biomicroscopy: right eye - Normal conjunctiva, pearly white sclera, smooth, shiny, transparent cornea, round, central, reflex pupil, central subcortical opacities. Left eye– Normal conjunctiva, pearly white sclera, smooth, shiny, transparent cornea, round, central, reflex pupil, central subcortical opacities.

Objective examination (Status praesens)

On objective examination he is having clear consciousness, hypersthenic. Peripheral lymph nodes are not palpable. Pale pink, dry skin and absent edema. BMI=24.22 (m=70kg; h=170cm) normal weight according to WHO. General condition of the patient's average severity. Cardiovascular system within limits of relative dullness of the heart without displacements. Rhythmic, sonorous heart sounds 120/80 mmHg FCC 87 b/min. Respiratory organs is free nasal breathing. Pulmonary sound on percussion. Auscultation - vesicular murmur, rales are absent. FR 18/min SpO2 97% Digestive system is moist, greasy tongue. Soft abdomen, painless on palpation. Liver at the costal margin. Regular intestinal transit. Organs of the urogenital system are painless and normal in urination. Giordano's sign bilaterally negative. Neuropsychiatric status is oriented to time and space. Responds appropriately to questions.

Therapeutic conduct:

The patient was referred to the pulmonologist to exclude latent TB. The pulmonologist was warned that due to the skin hyperreactivity in Behçet's disease, the Mantoux test may show a false positive result. It was recommended to perform the QuantiFERON TBC test. Initiated biological therapy with Infliximab 100mg + sol. NaCl 0.9 – 200ml in infusion. No adverse

reactions. The doctor recommended with to cancel the background treatment with tab. Sulfasalazin and to start tab. Metipred 4mg 2 tab/day - long-term tab. Pentoxifylline 400mg 1 tab/day - long-term and scheduled for repeated hospitalization for continuation of biological therapy with Infliximab

1.5 Diagnostic approaches for Bahcet’s disease

1.5.1 Diagnostic criteria

In 2014, it has been proposed to use international criteria for the diagnosis of BD (International Criteria for Behçet’s Disease (ICBD), which have a scoring system [16]:

Table 2: International Criteria for Behçet’s Disease (ICBD) [16].

Symptoms	Points
Ocular lesions (recurrent)	2
Oral aphthosis (recurrent)	2
Genital aphthosis (recurrent)	2
Skin lesions (recurrent)	1
Central nervous system	1
Vascular manifestations	1
Positive pathergy test	1

Note: a) a score of ≥ 4 points allows diagnosis of BD; b) the pathergy test is optional and is not taken into account in the initial scoring. However, where this test is performed, one additional point may be added for a positive result.

In 2019, there are six clinical phenotypes of BD, depending on the predominant symptoms [81]:

1. With mucocutaneous (isolated skin lesions (acneiform and papulopustular rashes, erythema nodosum) and mucous membranes (repeated ulcers of the oral mucosa and genitals), without severe organ disorders).
2. With joint lesions (dominated joint lesions of the type of non-deforming, non-erosive mono-/oligoarthritic of the lower extremities, with frequent enthesopathies. Sometimes joint lesions are accompanied by acne-like or pseudo-pustular rashes on the skin).
3. With vascular lesions (frequent repeated venous thromboses/Budd-Chiari syndrome/inferior vena cava syndrome/pulmonary artery aneurysms/less common – the arterial thromboses/cerebral venous sinus thromboses/intracardiac thrombosis; occurs predominantly

in men, characterized by high mortality).

4. With eye lesions (predominantly posterior/generalized, less common, anterior non-granulomatous, bilateral uveitis, occurs predominantly in men).
5. With parenchymatous CNS lesions (predominantly parenchymatous (focal) lesions of the diencephalic structures, brainstem, spinal cord; with characteristic of combined with eye lesions, predominance of men, high mortality).
6. With GIT lesions (ulcerative gastrointestinal tract lesions predominate, mainly in the ileocecal part of the intestine).

1.5.2 Imaging and laboratory tests

Till now there is no specific diagnostic test for BD. In some patients there is mild to moderate anemia, with neutrophilic leucocytosis, and elevated thrombocyte. In the active phase, the levels of acute phase proteins (CRP, neopterin, (SAA)), proinflammatory cytokines, calprotectin, ESR, rheumatoid factor, α 1-antitrypsin, α 2-macroglobulin, etc. increase. The content of serum immunoglobulins, especially IgA, also increases, cryoglobulinemia can be determined, but, as a rule, antinuclear and antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies are absent. An increase in fecal (not serum) calprotectin is associated with an exacerbation of the intestinal form of BD [103]. In 28-49% of patients with gastrointestinal lesions, antibodies to saccharomyces yeast (ASCA (IgA and IgG) are detected, in 67.5% - antibodies to α -enolase IgM [82]. Approximately 60% of patients are positive for HLA-B5 (51), and in some countries (Japan) - HLA-A10 (26) antigens. No association was noted between HLA B5 (51) positivity and any clinical manifestations and severity of BD. HLA B5 (51) positivity is not a diagnostic criterion for BD [16].

For neuro-bahcet neuroimaging has a main role in diagnosis. MRI considered number one neuro-imaging modality. MRI abnormalities have been well-described in NBD. The consensus characteristics of MRI lesions are: In Acute/subacute lesions there is a hypo-intense - iso-intense on T1-weighted (T1W) images, commonly enhanced with contrast on gadolinium-T1W images, and hyper-intense on T2W and FLAIR images. In chronic phase, mainly smaller lesions which is usually non-enhancing, but may resolve fully. Evidence of atrophy mainly on the brainstem. Nonspecific white matter lesions also seen

MRI is extremely useful in differentiating NBD from its mimics. The brainstem–thalamic–basal ganglia lesions, in the proper background very useful in the diagnosis of acute/subacute parenchymal NBD. Chronic parenchymal NBD lesions are iso-intense, very small, sometimes hard to choose between BD and lesions of multiple sclerosis. Normally, multiple sclerosis lesions are more often periventricular, no frequent involvement of the basal ganglia, internal

capsule, and the peripheral part of the pons, while in chronic parenchymal NBD lesions are predominantly subcortical. Brainstem atrophy in association with subcortical lesions points toward NBD [47].

Figure 5: T2 weighted MRI sequences showing typical presentation of NBD with an association of brainstem and midbrain hypersignal lesions [65]

Figure 6: Flair weighted MRI sequences of two patients showing atypical presentations of neurobehçet disease [65]

Figure 7: Flair weighted MRI sequences showing brainstem lesions with ventral localization [65].

CSF constituents are altered in almost 70-80% patients. CSF protein has moderately raised in most cases, and oligoclonal bands are usually absent. The CSF cell count is increased in 60–80 % of parenchymal NBD cases (range 0–400 × 10 cells/L) and there could be CSF neutrophilia, lymphocytosis, or mixed cellularity. CSF glucose is usually normal in NBD and low levels point toward CNS infections. [28].

Serum IL-6 levels have been related to BD disease, eventhogghh the findings are not constantly reported. Incresed CSF levels of IL-6 have been seen in patients with acute parenchymal NBD. A very smaller rise in IL-6 levels has also been reported in a proportion of progressive parenchymal NBD. Increased CSF IL-6 levels are formly linked with raised CSF cell count and protein, and these three parameters have been associated with disease activity and outcome over 3 years. In sometimes elevated CSF IL-6 levels were counted in the presence of normal CSF cells and protein. Collectively, these data indicate that IL-6 is not a reliable biomarker of NBD or BD[28] [38].

1.5.3 Pathergy test.

Pathergy phenomenon was described first in 1937 by Blobner as a state of altered tissue reactivity in response to minor trauma. A very unique feature of the inflammation seen in BD is the presence of the pathergy phenomenon, when a person got any type of injury types of inflammatory stimuli to tissues cause an enhanced inflammatory response. The pathergy phenomenon is not limited to the skin. Angiography or endovascular intervention on arteries

can lead to arterial thrombosis and/or the formation of an arterial aneurysm; person can sometimes develop post-injection phlebitis often after venipuncture; intraocular injections of GC can lead to an increase in intraocular inflammation; and surgical treatment of ulcerative bowel lesions can result in ulcers in the area of anastomosis [71]. Histopathological examination of this phenomenon reveals an inflammatory infiltrate with a predominance of mononuclear cells around cutaneous vessels and an increase in the number of mast cells. Neutrophilic infiltration of blood vessels may also be present. Some comparative study of skin immune responses to needle prick injury between a control group of healthy volunteers and patients with BD and a positive pathergy skin test showed that, in contrast to the self-limited inflammatory responses due to the innate immune response observed in normal skin during the first 8 h, in patients with BD, an increased Th1-type inflammatory response developed at the point of injection after 48 h which is characterized by a marked influx of mature dendritic cells, monocytes and CD4+ T lymphocytes, an enhanced content of Th1-type cytokines (IFN- γ , IL-12 p40, IL-15) and chemokines (MIP3-alpha, IP-10, Mig and iTac), along with adhesion molecules (ICAM-1, VCAM-1) at the point of injection injury[55]. The positivity of this test in patients with BD is higher among men and fluctuates within 25-75%. For example, among peoples from Middle East this percentage is 60%, among Koreans - 15%. Patients living in the UK and the USA, the percentage is even lower - 5-10%. Among the cohort of patients at the Research Institute of Rheumatology, a positive pathergy skin test was detected in 30% of cases[17].

The test procedure is intradermal, subcutaneous, and intravenous in methods. Although intradermal needle prick is used commonly this testing, various doctors have also used the intradermal injection of normal saline, monosodium urate crystals, or streptococcal antigens to perform the test [80]. In addition, two types of pathergy tests are available first an oral pathergy test (OPT) and a skin pathergy test (SPT). For the OPT, the procedure entails pricking the mucous membrane on the lower lip to the level of the submucosa with a 20-gauge blunt disposable needle. Although the sensitivity is very less for OPT while comparing to the SPT. The OPT is very easier to assess because an ulcer or pustule of any size is meant to be positive, no need to measure the size of the lesion[55]. Take forearm, on the medial side an injection is made at 4 points with a sterile large-diameter needle. After 48 hours, a papule or pustule more than 2 mm in diameter appears at the injection site and which run out after 3-4 days (Figure 10). The pathergy reaction is not so constant, it changes at different periods of the disease, as a rule, it is not associated with an exacerbation of the disease or any other clinical features of BD. It is believed that if the test is positive, then it has diagnostic value, but its absence does not say that patient has no BD[80].

Table 3: Grading and definitions of skin pathergy test [104]

<i>Grades of SPT*</i>	<i>Characteristics of the pathergy reaction at 48 hours</i>	
	<i>Blunt needles</i>	<i>Sharp needles</i>
Negative (-)	Only erythema or trace of prick	Only erythema or trace of prick
Suspect (\pm)	Papule <2 mm + erythema	
Positive (+)		
1 +	Papule 2-3 mm + erythema	Papule \leq 3 mm + erythema
2 +	Papule >3 mm + erythema	Papule >3 mm + erythema
3 +	Pustule 1-2 mm	Pustule 1-2 mm
4 +	Pustule >2 mm	Pustule >2 mm

*SPT = Skin pathergy test.

Figure 8: OPT: mucous membrane of the lower lip is pricked with a 20 gauge blunt disposable needle[12]

Figure 9: Pathergy test positivity showing erythematous papules and pustules[12]

1.6 Differential diagnosis

Idiopathic recurrent aphthous stomatitis is characteristic of 20% of the general population as an independent disease. Data shows that in 14-55% of patients with BD, recurrent aphthous stomatitis expressed itself as large or herpetiform aphthae, in contrast to patients with idiopathic recurrent aphthous stomatitis, for whom small aphthae are more typical, and large or herpetiform ones occur only for 9% [22]. recurrent aphthous stomatitis as a symptom is very often seen in patients who have systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), and Reiter's syndrome [10].

The mucocutaneous diseases manifested by non-aphthous lesions of the oral and genital mucosa also need to be differentiated with BD. Particularly problematic in this context are patients with erythema multiforme, autoimmune bullous dermatoses such as pemphigus vulgaris, and the vulvovaginal form of erosive lichen planus. Changes like erythema nodosum, characteristic of BD, should be differentiated from idiopathic or associated with sarcoidosis, infection, IBD, oncological diseases, and the use of certain medications. In addition to BD, neutrophilic dermatoses also include Sweet's syndrome, neutrophilic eccrine hidradenitis,

gangrenosum pyoderma, dermatosis-arthritis syndrome associated with the intestine, rheumatoid neutrophilic dermatitis, and Still's disease in adults, which should be considered in the differential diagnosis of BD [68].

Table 4: differential diagnosis of BD [73, 105, 106]

Diagnosis	Characteristics of ulcers	Involvement of other organs and systems	Diagnostic features	Specific laboratory indicators
Recurrent aphthous stomatitis	Recurrent aphthae of the oral mucosa, often small	Absent	Absent	HLA B12

Dermatological diseases:

Stevens Johnson Syndrome	Blisters with subsequent formation of bleeding erosions, covered with a fibrinous film	Maculopapular rash, purulent blepharoconjunctivitis, iridocyclitis	Association with taking medicines	Absent
Pemphigus (acantholytic)	Blisters with the formation of bright red, slightly painful erosions on the	Blisters on the skin	Nikolsky's Symptom	Acantholytic cells in smears, prints from the bottom of fresh erosions during

	<p>mucous membrane of the mouth, nose, pharynx, red border of the lips</p>			<p>cytological examination; IgG autoantibodies against antigens of the intercellular binding substance</p>
<p>Erosive ulcerative form of lichen planus</p>	<p>Most often small superficial single or multiple erosions, less often ulcers of irregular outlines, covered with fibrous plaque, after removal of which bleeding is observed, painless. Characterized by long-term existence of</p>	<p>Erosions and papules on the skin and mucous membranes of the genitals, often with scalloped edges, from 1 to 4–5 cm or more in size</p>	<p>More common in women. Tendency to grouped arrangement of rashes with the formation of rings, garlands, lines. In most cases, the rash is accompanied by itching, localized symmetrically on the flexor surfaces of</p>	<p>Characteristic picture in histological and cytological examination of the skin</p>

	erosions and ulcers, around which typical whitish		the extremities, trunk, genitals	
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Systemic diseases:

SLE	Whitish eroded plaques with rough edges	Characteristic skin lesions - erythema of the malar region, discoid lesions, generalized erythematous rashes. genital ulcers are not typical	Systemic manifestations (kidney damage, CNS, joints, etc.) – criteria for SLE diagnosis	Immunological: antinuclear factor, antibodies to DNA
Reiter's syndrome	Painless mouth ulcers	Conjunctivitis, urethritis, balanitis, Arthritis, keratoderma	Chronological relationship of infection with onset of disease, detection of chlamydia or intestinal infection	HLA-B27
IBD (More often Crohn's disease, less often	More often solitary, relapses less often	Ulcerative bowel lesion 100%, genital ulcers rare, pathergy test	Less common skin and eye lesions, not characteristic –	Characteristic histology picture of intestinal biopsy

nonspecific ulcerative colitis)		not characteristic	CNS. Characteristic endoscopic picture	specimens
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1.7 Management of Behcet's disease

BD is a chronic disease, which is characterized by exacerbations and remissions. The main thing is that therapy should be carried out throughout life. At the same time it doesn't give always a good results, which means treatment strategy mainly depends on the manifestations and severity of the disease in each individual patient. In the other way for an example, the obviously poor prognosis in men who fell ill at the age of up to 25 years. Early diagnosis and best treatment are the main conditions that reduce the development of serious effects and complications of BD, such as damage to the central nervous system and complete loss of vision[9]. In therapy, BD has a wide range of drugs used, which is determined mainly by the variety of clinical manifestations of the disease itself - from relatively mild to extremely severe symptoms in prognostic terms and the variability of the natural course of BD. The drawback in the treatment is the efficacy of only a limited number of drugs used in BD has been proven in RCTs, while the use of the vast majority of other drugs is based on experience gained from observational studies [37],[57]. RCTs conducted to date in BD have mainly focused on the treatment of mucocutaneous and ophthalmological manifestations, without addressing vascular, neurological, and gastrointestinal symptoms.

The European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) guidelines for the treatment of BD which has a regular update over every 10 years. The latest version of 2018 has five new general principles and one additional recommendation on surgical treatment of vascular lesions. The core principles emphasize the importance of multidisciplinary collaboration for optimal patient care and define the goal of treatment as rapid suppression of inflammation to prevent the development of irreversible organ damage [37].

1.7.1 Pharmacological treatment

For Mucocutaneous manifestations, Glucocorticoids (GC) should be used locally to treat oral and genital mucosal ulcers. Colchicine should be used to prevent recurrence of mucocutaneous manifestations, primarily erythema nodosum and genital ulcers. Local and/or systemic cosmetics used in the treatment of acne vulgaris are additionally recommended for papulopustular and/or acne-like eruptions. Leg ulcers in BB may be due to chronic venous

insufficiency or obliterating vasculitis, and therefore the care of such patients should be carried out in conjunction with dermatologists and/or vascular surgeons. In refractory cases, drugs such as azathioprine (AZA), thalidomide, interferon- α (IFN- α), tumor necrosis factor- α inhibitors (TNF- α) and apremilast should be prescribed [58].

Eye involvements are much serious to take in consideration. Treatment of uveitis in patients with BD requires close cooperation with ophthalmologists, the goal of therapy is to achieve and maintain remission. Any patient with BD and inflammatory ocular disease involving the posterior segment of the eye should receive AZA, cyclosporine (CsA), IFN- α . For primary or recurrent episodes of acute uveitis threatening vision loss, high doses of GC, IFN- α are indicated. In case of Isolated anterior uveitis systemic administration of immunosuppressants is indicated for patients who have poor prognostic factors like young age, male gender and early age of onset of BD.

In Acute deep vein thrombosis in BD, GCs and immunosuppressants such as AZA, cyclophosphamide (CP) or CsA are used. While in refractory venous thrombosis refractory to therapy are indicated for treatment with TNF- α . Anticoagulants may be considered if the risk of bleeding is low and pulmonary artery aneurysms have been excluded. In Arterial lesions High-dose GC and CYC are recommended for the treatment of pulmonary artery aneurysms in BD. In refractory cases, TNF- α inhibitors should be used. In patients with pulmonary hemorrhage or high risk of bleeding, arterial embolization is the treatment of choice rather than open surgery. In patients with peripheral arterial or aortic aneurysms, conservative treatment with GC and CYC should precede surgical intervention. In case of life-threatening symptoms, arterial stenting is recommended [26].

GI involvement in BD conformation should be done by an endoscopic and/or other imaging methods. NSAID-related ulcers, IBD, and infections such as tuberculosis should be excluded. In refractory/severe GI involvement urgent surgical consultation is recommended in case of perforation, intestinal obstruction, and GI bleeding. During exacerbation of GI involvement in patients with BD, the use of GC in combination with disease-modifying drugs such as 5-aminosalicylic acid derivatives (sulfasalazine, mesalazine) or AZA is indicated.

CNS involvement in acute parenchymatous CNS involvement in BD, high doses of GCs should be used and slowly taper the dosage, along with immunosuppressants, such as AZA. CsA should be avoided in these patients. Monoclonal antibodies to TNF- α are used as first-line drugs in severe CNS involvement or in refractory patients. The first episode of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis requires high doses of GCs with subsequent slow reduction. Anticoagulants should given for a small period, while screening for extracranial vascular involvement should

be performed.

Joint involvement in patients with acute arthritis the primary treatment is with colchicine. Acute monoarthritis can be cured with intra-articular administration of GC[26, 37, 58].

Table 5: Modern approaches to the treatment of various clinical manifestations of BD (supplement to the 2018 EULAR recommendations) [6].

Clinical manifestations of BD	First line drugs	Second line drugs	Experimental drugs
Mucocutaneous	Colchicine GC (low doses orally/ topically)	Azathioprine Apremilast TNF α inhibitors Interferon- α	Anti-IL1 Ustekinumab Secukinumab
Joint involvement	Colchicine Salazopyrin Methotrexate	TNF α inhibitor Interferon- α	Anti-IL1 Sucukinumab
Eye damage	Azathioprine Cyclosporin A	TNF α inhibitor Interferon- α	Tocilizumab
Vascular damage	Azathioprine (venous/ arterial) Cyclosporin A (venous) Cyclophosphamide (arterial)	TNF α inhibitor Interferon- α	Tocilizumab
Gastrointestinal damage	Salazopyrin Azathioprine	TNF α inhibitors	Anti-IL-1 Tocilizumab
Neurological	Azathioprine Mycophenolate mofetil	TNF α inhibitors Interferon- α Cyclophosphamide	Tocilizumab

Dosing, colchicine 0.5–2 mg/day; azathioprine, 2–2.5 mg/kg/day, glucocorticoids: low-dose, 5–10 mg/day prednisolone; Salazopyrin, 0.5–3 g/day, methotrexate, 5–25 mg/week; cyclophosphamide, 0.5–1 g/month; cyclosporine A, 3–5 mg/kg/day; mycophenolate mofetil, 0.5–3 g/day; apremilast, 60 mg/day; Interferon- α , 3–9 million IU/3–7 d weekly; TNF α inhibitors: infliximab, 3–10 mg/kg/4–8 weekly, adalimumab, 40 mg/SC/1-2 weekly; IL-1

antagonists: anakinra, 100–200 mg/SC daily; canakinumab, 150–300 mg/2–4 weekly; tocilizumab, 4–8 mg/kg/4 weekly, 162 mg/weekly SC; ustekinumab, 45–90 mg/4–8 weekly; secukinumab, 150–300 mg/4–8 weekly

1.7.2 Biological agents:

TNF- α inhibitors is one of the main proinflammatory cytokines that have an important pathogenetic significance in BD, and its inhibition leads to a decrease in the severity of almost all clinical manifestations. The effectiveness of TNF- α , primarily INF and adalimumab, has also been shown in cases of CNS and gastrointestinal tract lesions, pulmonary artery aneurysms, and other vascular manifestations [42]. Most patients, in addition to TNF- α , received immunosuppressants, like methotrexate and AZA, and in cases of gastrointestinal tract lesions, given with 5-aminosalicylic acid derivatives. In Japan, INF and adalimumab are officially approved for the treatment of the intestinal form of BD[39]. According to the EULAR recommendations, IFN- α should be prescribed in cases of severe damage to the eyes, central nervous system, gastrointestinal tract and blood vessels, as well as in cases of ineffectiveness of standard immunosuppressants and GCs. Most researchers used INF at a dose of 5 mg / kg every 4-6 weeks, in case of insufficient effectiveness of the drug, the dose was increased to 10 mg / kg. ADA was prescribed in a standard dosage - 40 mg subcutaneously every 2 weeks. In BD, other TNF- α inhibitors (golimumab, certolizumab pegol) can be used with good efficiency (94.1%), in cases refractory to INF and adalimumab. The use of certolizumab pegol is more advisable in pregnant patients with active BD requiring the use of TNF- α inhibitors, since this drug don't intervene the placental barrier. Unlike IFN- α , remission after the withdrawal of TNF- α inhibitors lasts no more than 2 months. The main adverse events associated with TNF- α inhibitor therapy are infectious complications and reactivation of latent tuberculosis infection. The development of skin psoriasis, SLE-like autoimmune syndrome, and demyelinating leukoencephalopathy resembling multiple sclerosis have also found[87].

IL-1 inhibitors are an approved one rheumatology for the treatment of RA and autoinflammatory diseases. The efficacy of IL-1 (anakinra and canakinumab) in patients with BD has been studied in several multicentre retrospective studies have noted the good efficacy of IL-1, mainly in relation to the ophthalmological manifestations of BD. when prescribing anakinra to patients with ineffective TNF- α noted a rapid effect of the drug after 1-2 weeks, however, almost all patients, on average, after 29 weeks, noted an exacerbation of mainly mucocutaneous manifestations of BD [14]. In contrast, in a pilot study showed that 2 of 6 patients receiving anakinra for mucocutaneous manifestations of BD achieved complete remission, 2 - partial, and with an increase in the dose of the drug to 200 mg / day, its

effectiveness against aphthous stomatitis and genital ulcers significantly improved [32]. Indications for canakinumab administration in patients with BD in most cases described in the literature were severe manifestations refractory to standard therapy and TNF- α , such as uveitis, vascular and gastrointestinal lesions. In some cases, more frequent administration of the standard dose of the drug was required to achieve a clinical effect - 150 mg every 6 weeks instead of 8 weeks [88]

IL-6 inhibitors, primarily tocilizumab (TCZ), are approved in rheumatology for the treatment of RA, juvenile idiopathic arthritis, and giant cell arteritis. There have been no RCTs studying IL-6 in BD. In 2017, an article published based on the results of therapy for 47 patients with TCZ and was most effective in relation to symptoms of severe, usually refractory to IFN- α , parenchymal damage to the central nervous system, eyes, and blood vessels, as well as in 2 patients with secondary amyloidosis. The use of TCZ allowed to reduce the maintenance dose of GCs, and in some cases to completely eliminate them - remission without GCs was achieved in 11 of 21 patients with uveitis and in 3 of 6 patients with neurological damage. However, TCZ was not effective enough in relation to other symptoms of BD - mucocutaneous, joint and gastrointestinal damage, and in some cases led to worsening of mucocutaneous symptoms. TCZ in BD is used in standard dosages - 162 mg / week subcutaneously or 8 mg / kg intravenously every 4 weeks [3].

Rituximab (RTM) is a chimeric monoclonal antibody with specificity for the CD20 antigen, which is expressed exclusively on B lymphocytes. The drug is approved for the treatment of RA and ANCA-associated vasculitis. It is rarely used in BD.

Daclizumab is a humanized monoclonal antibody against CD25, the alpha chain of the IL-2 receptor. The drug was approved in Europe for the treatment of graft rejection after organ transplantation, administered intravenously, at a starting dose of 1 mg/kg once every 2 weeks, with dose and adjusted frequency in response and side effects to a maximum of 200 mg. It is well tolerated by patients in the management of uveitis, with side effects including lymphadenopathy, psoriaform rashes, mild peripheral oedema and infections are seen. Despite showing promise in the treatment of non-Behçet's uveitis, daclizumab was discontinued by the manufacturer in 2009 due to decreasing market demand [63].

1.7.3 Emerging direction

Oral phosphodiesterase-4 (PDE4) inhibitor Apremilast has been the first used for BD is promising therapy in future. Its action by increasing intracellular cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) levels, it downregulates pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , interleukin (IL)-17, and IL-8 with promoting the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10. Its well

worked in psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis and has a favourable safety profile Apremilast is well-tolerated, with a safety profile consistent across Behçet's syndrome, psoriasis, and psoriatic arthritis studies [64]. Some side effects such as diarrhea and nausea, headache, and upper respiratory infections. No deaths were associated with apremilast in Behçet's syndrome trials. Apremilast represents a valuable addition to the Behçet's syndrome treatment arsenal, particularly for patients with refractory oral ulcers. A more recent study with another PDE4 inhibitor, roflumilast, suggests that this is another promising agent for BD [83].

Tofacitinib and baricitinib JANUS KINASE (JAK) inhibitors very effective in remission in Behçet's vascular involvement. It decreases the inflammation inhibiting the JAK-STAT pathway. This drugs and stops the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, which are mostly increased in BD. It acts on specific Cytokines. The JAK inhibitors can block signaling downstream of cytokines like IL-6, IL-12, and IL-23, which are implicated in BD. This inhibitor may help alleviate symptoms such as oral and genital ulcers, skin lesions, and uveitis by controlling the underlying inflammatory process [59].

2 DISCUSSION

Behçet's disease (BD) is a very serious, systemic vasculitis characterized by oral and genital ulcers, uveitis, and various other systemic symptoms, which poses a significant challenge to the diagnosis of BD. This discussion paper is a scientific review of BD, using current research and clinical perspectives to elucidate its etiopathogenesis, diagnostic methods, and existing treatment options. The exact cause of BD is still unclear, but recent studies indicate that several symptoms make BD understandable. The occurrence of BD has different factors when analysing geographical areas, with high rates found in countries along the Silk Road, especially Turkey, Iran, Iraq, and East Asia. This distribution pattern shows the ancient trade route. migration patterns. Turkey has the highest prevalence of 420 per 100,000 population.

Presentation of BD, having recurrent oral and genital ulcers, skin lesions, ocular inflammation. First manifestation is painful recurrent aphthous ulcers occurring in most of the patient. While genital ulcers are not so often comparing to oral one which arise on the scrotum or vulva and heal with scarring. Anterior or posterior uveitis with redness, pain, and if not treated permanent loss of vision. cutaneous markers include the erythema nodosum-like skin lesions acneiform nodules, and pseudofolliculitis. While Joint, gastrointestinal, vascular and neurological involvement can also seen. International Study Group suggest a need of oral ulcers plus two of four hallmarks which is genital ulcers, eye lesions, skin lesions, or a positive pathergy test. Hypersensitivity skin reaction is pathergy test, in which a needle prick shows a papule or pustule. Positive for HLA-B51 suggest BD but not accurate. In some case atypical presentations without the oral ulcers may cause diagnosis difficult. The etiopathogenesis of Behçet's disease remains very challenging since now the models shows environmental factors in genetically predisposed individuals elicit innate and adaptive immune responses. Genome-wide studies have identified variants in IL10, IL23R, CCR1, STAT4, KLRC4, ERAP1, and FUT2 genes as disease risk factors.

In 2018, Yazici et al. depicted, how it is categorized as an autoinflammatory illness. The pathophysiology of BD hac connection with deregulation of the innate immune system, and the authors highlighted the the efficacy of treatments that target these pathways, such as IL-1 inhibitors [90]. There are studies shows the role of innate immune system dysregulation in the pathogenesis of Bechet's disease. Genetic studies have identified links between BD and mutations in genes involved in the regulation of innate immunity, such as MEFV, IL-1 β , and IL-10 [53] According to the study, patients with Bechet's disease had higher concentrations of these cell types, Aktas Cetin et al. analysed the possibility of Th22 and Th17 cells that secrete

IL-22 and IFN- γ in BD[4]. In his study the patients with BD had higher concentrations of these cell types, which shows cells involved in inflammation has relation between innate and adaptive immune responses and patients has BD have levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α , these are the cells mediate innate response. IL-1 has been studied as potential treatment target in Behçet's disease. Anakinra, an IL-1 receptor antagonist is ready to use to treat a case series of individuals with drug-resistant BD, according to Cantarini et al [14]. The results trail are supporting pathophysiological function of IL-1 in BD and the therapeutic potential of targeting innate immunity pathways. A study assessing the safety and effectiveness of anti-interleukin-1 therapy in Bechet's disease was carried out by Emmi et al [24]. This study support to the diagnosis of Bechet's disease as an autoinflammatory disorder and treating via innate immunity modulations. Drugs like azathioprine, cyclosporine, cyclophosphamide, or methotrexate are for organ-threatening manfesations. TNF- α inhibitors, infliximab, adalimumab, and golimumab have are best in ocular, mucocutaneous, joint, vascular, and neurological problems Drugs like anakinra and canakinumab which blocks the interleukin-1 blocking agents have best results in vascular and rheumatological manifestations. Anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody used for best results in patients having ocular and central nervous system disease [6].

Patients are very prone with psychosocial burden in case of chronic illness. Coping with painful and uncertain prognosis, and treatment side effects takes ia very challanging. Neurotic condition like anxiety, depression, and social isolation are often. An approach with counselling, stress reduction techniques, and peer support, is effective with medical management. Awareness about psychoneuroimmunology and biopsychosocial perspectives in BD is most needed.

CONCLUSION

1. Behçet's disease is a complex, systemic vasculitis having diverse manifestation ranging from frequent oral and genital ulcers, uveitis, and various organ manifestations. Advancing medical field has been understanding clinical manifestations and way of managements still lacks the pathophysiology remains unclear, which shows increased need of future research to improve the management and diagnosing strategies. BD geographical distribution very challenging since distributed along the silk route, which is ancient way of trade and migration, with the highest prevalence particularly in Turkey, Iran, and East Asia. Excibiton varies significantly across different regions and among the ethnic peoples.
2. The pathogenesis of BD is very connected interplay of genetic predisposition, the HLA-B51 allele, environmental factors and infections. Dysregulation of innate and adaptive immune responses which include the neutrophil initiation and cytokine imbalances elevate the disease's development and progression.
3. Clinical manifestations range from mucocutaneous lesions (oral and genital ulcers), ocular involvement (uveitis), vascular manifestations (thrombosis and aneurysms), neurological symptoms, and gastrointestinal issues. The diversity of BD is very challenging treat.
4. Diagnosing Behçet's disease mainly on the factors on clinical criteria, including often oral ulcers and other systemic manifestations. Positive for HLA B51 is strong trait for diagnosis also the pathergy test is a diagnostic criterion since it can be false positive, still remains a diagnostic test.
5. BD requires an approach from various department since there is no exact diagnostic tool. Corticosteroids, immunosuppressants, and biologic agents like TNF- α inhibitors are the current management plans. Therapies targeting immune pathways like IL-1 and JAK inhibitors has best result but till needed close evaluation. Early finding and prevention initially are crucial.

REFERENCES

1. Abdolmohammadi R, Bonyadi M (2016) Polymorphisms of Promoter Region of TNF- α Gene in Iranian Azeri Turkish Patients with Behçet's Disease. *J Korean Med Sci* 32:33. doi: 10.3346/JKMS.2017.32.1.33
2. Accorinti M, Pesci FR, Pirraglia MP, Abicca I, Pivetti-Pezzi P (2017) Ocular Behçet's Disease: Changing Patterns Over Time, Complications and Long-Term Visual Prognosis. *Ocul Immunol Inflamm* 25:29–36. doi: 10.3109/09273948.2015.1094095
3. Akiyama M, Kaneko Y, Takeuchi T (2020) Effectiveness of tocilizumab in Behçet's disease: A systematic literature review. *Semin Arthritis Rheum* 50:797–804. doi: 10.1016/J.SEMARTHRT.2020.05.017
4. Aktas Cetin E, Cosan F, Cefle A, Deniz G (2014) IL-22-secreting Th22 and IFN- γ -secreting Th17 cells in Behçet's disease. *Mod Rheumatol* 24:802–807. doi: 10.3109/14397595.2013.879414
5. Aldinucci A, Bonechi E, Biagioli T, Repice AM, D'Elis MM, Emmi L, Emmi G, Silvestri E, Barilaro A, Ballerini C (2018) CSF/serum matrix metalloproteinase-9 ratio discriminates neuro Behçet from multiple sclerosis. *Ann Clin Transl Neurol* 5:493–498. doi: 10.1002/ACN3.538
6. Alibaz-Oner F, Direskeneli H (2021) Advances in the Treatment of Behçet's Disease. *Curr Rheumatol Rep* 23. doi: 10.1007/S11926-021-01011-Z
7. Alibaz-Oner F, Direskeneli H (2022) Update on the Diagnosis of Behçet's Disease. *Diagnostics (Basel)* 13. doi: 10.3390/DIAGNOSTICS13010041
8. Alibaz-Oner F, Mumcu G, Kubilay Z, Ozen G, Celik G, Karadeniz A, Can M, Oner SY, Inanc N, Atagunduz P, Ergun T, Direskeneli H (2014) Unmet need in Behçet's disease: most patients in routine follow-up continue to have oral ulcers. *Clin Rheumatol* 33:1773–1776. doi: 10.1007/S10067-014-2585-3
9. Alpsoy E (2016) Behçet's disease: A comprehensive review with a focus on epidemiology, etiology and clinical features, and management of mucocutaneous lesions. *Journal of Dermatology* 43:620–632. doi: 10.1111/1346-8138.13381
10. Baş Y, Seçkin HY, Kalkan G, Takcı Z, Önder Y, Çıtıl R, Demir S, Şahin Ş (2016) Investigation of Behçet's Disease and Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis Frequency: The Highest Prevalence in Turkey. *Balkan Med J* 33:390. doi: 10.5152/BALKANMEDJ.2016.15101
11. Becatti M, Emmi G, Bettiol A, Silvestri E, Di Scala G, Taddei N, Prisco D, Fiorillo C (2019) Behçet's syndrome as a tool to dissect the mechanisms of thrombo-inflammation: clinical and pathogenetic aspects. *Clin Exp Immunol* 195:322–333. doi: 10.1111/CEI.13243
12. Bostan E, Gulseren D, Akdogan N, Ozdemir DA, Karadag O (2022) A diagnostic challenge: Pathergy positivity in papulopustular lesions of Behçet disease mimicking acute localised exanthematous pustulosis. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol* 88:817–819. doi: 10.25259/IJDVL_1044_2021
13. Brown MA, Xu H, Li Z (2020) Genetics and the axial spondyloarthritis spectrum. *Rheumatology (Oxford)* 59:IV58–IV66. doi: 10.1093/RHEUMATOLOGY/KEAA464
14. Cantarini L, Vitale A, Scalini P, Dinarello CA, Rigante D, Franceschini R, Simonini G, Borsari G, Caso F, Lucherini OM, Frediani B, Bertoldi I, Punzi L, Galeazzi M, Cimaz R (2015) Anakinra treatment in drug-resistant Behçet's disease: a case series. *Clin Rheumatol* 34:1293–1301. doi: 10.1007/S10067-013-2443-8
15. Cho S Bin, Cho S, Bang D (2012) New insights in the clinical understanding of Behçet's disease. *Yonsei Med J* 53:35–42. doi: 10.3349/YMJ.2012.53.1.35
16. Davatchi F, Assaad-Khalil S, Calamia † K T, Crook JE, Sadeghi-Abdollahi B, Schirmer M, Tzellos T, Zouboulis CC, Akhlagi M, Al-Dalaan A, Alekberova ZS, Ali AA, Altenburg A, Arromdee E, Baltaci M, Bastos M, Benamour S, Ghorbel I Ben, Boyvat A,

- Carvalho L, Chen W, Ben-Chetrit E, Chams-Davatchi C, Correia JA, Crespo J, Dias C, Dong Y, Paix~ Ao-Duarte F, Elmuntaser K, Elonakov A V, Gra~ J, Gil N, Haghdoost A-A, Hayani RM, Houman H, Isayeva AR, Jamshidi AR, Kaklamani P, Kumar A, Kyrgidis A, Madanat W, Nadji A, Namba K, Ohno S, Olivieri I, Patto JV, Pipitone N, De Queiroz M V, Ramos F, Resende C, Rosa CM, Salvarani C, Serra MJ, Shahram F, Shams H, Sharquie KE, Sliti-Khanfir M, Tribolet De Abreu T, Vasconcelos C, Vedes J, Wechsler B, Cheng YK, Zhang Z, Ziaei N (2014) The International Criteria for Behçet's Disease (ICBD): a collaborative study of 27 countries on the sensitivity and specificity of the new criteria. *JEADV* 28:338–347. doi: 10.1111/jdv.12107
17. Davatchi F, Chams-Davatchi C, Ghodsi Z, Shahram F, Nadji A, Shams H, Akhlaghi M, Larimi R, Sadeghi-Abdolahi B (2011) Diagnostic value of pathergy test in Behçet's disease according to the change of incidence over the time. *Clin Rheumatol* 30:1151–1155. doi: 10.1007/S10067-011-1694-5
 18. Demirtürk OS, Tünel HA, Alemdaroğlu U, Demirtürk OS, Tünel HA, Alemdaroğlu U (2017) Vascular Manifestations of Behçet's Disease. *Behçet's Disease*. doi: 10.5772/INTECHOPEN.68765
 19. Deniz R, Tulunay-Virlan A, Ture Ozdemir F, Unal AU, Ozen G, Alibaz-Oner F, Aydin-Tatli I, Mumcu G, Ergun T, Direskeneli H (2017) Th17-Inducing Conditions Lead to in vitro Activation of Both Th17 and Th1 Responses in Behçet's Disease. *Immunol Invest* 46:518–525. doi: 10.1080/08820139.2017.1306865
 20. Desbois AC, Rautou PE, Biard L, Belmatoug N, Wechsler B, Resche-Rigon M, Zarrouk V, Fantin B, De Chambrun MP, Cacoub P, Valla D, Saadoun D, Plessier A (2014) Behçet's disease in Budd-Chiari syndrome. *Orphanet J Rare Dis* 9. doi: 10.1186/S13023-014-0153-1
 21. Ecem G, Nuhoglu K, Nuhoglu C, Osoydan M, Arslan B (2024) Dr. Hulusi Behçet: A Pioneer in Dermatology and the Legacy of Behçet's Disease. *Cureus* 16:e69600. doi: 10.7759/CUREUS.69600
 22. Elias ML, Fatahzadeh M, Schwartz RA (2022) Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis: An Enigmatic Entity and Sign of Systemic Disease. *Indian J Dermatol* 67:834. doi: 10.4103/IJD.IJD_971_20
 23. Emmi G, Bettiol A, Silvestri E, Di Scala G, Becatti M, Fiorillo C, Prisco D (2019) Vascular Behçet's syndrome: an update. *Intern Emerg Med* 14:645–652. doi: 10.1007/S11739-018-1991-Y
 24. Emmi G, Talarico R, Lopalco G, Cimaz R, Cantini F, Viapiana O, Olivieri I, Goldoni M, Vitale A, Silvestri E, Prisco D, Lapadula G, Galeazzi M, Iannone F, Cantarini L (2016) Efficacy and safety profile of anti-interleukin-1 treatment in Behçet's disease: a multicenter retrospective study. *Clin Rheumatol* 35:1281–1286. doi: 10.1007/S10067-015-3004-0
 25. Ergun T, Cao W, Napier RJ, Mattioli I, Bettiol A, Saruhan-Direskeneli G, Direskeneli H, Emmi G (2021) Pathogenesis of Behçet's Syndrome: Genetic, Environmental and Immunological Factors. *Frontiers in Medicine* | www.frontiersin.org 8. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2021.713052
 26. Esatoglu SN, Hatemi G (2019) Update on the treatment of Behçet's syndrome. *Intern Emerg Med* 14:661–675. doi: 10.1007/S11739-019-02035-1
 27. Fabiani C, Vitale A, Orlando I, Sota J, Capozzoli M, Franceschini R, Galeazzi M, Tosi GM, Frediani B, Cantarini L (2017) Quality of life impairment in Behçet's disease and relationship with disease activity: a prospective study. *Intern Emerg Med* 12:947–955. doi: 10.1007/S11739-017-1691-Z
 28. Ferraro D, Franciotta D, Bedin R, Solaro C, Cocco E, Santangelo M, Immovilli P, Gajofatto A, Calabrese M, Di Filippo M, Orlandi R, Simone AM, Vitetta F, Capello E, Giunti D, Murialdo A, Frau J, Mariotto S, Gallina A, Gasperini C, Sola P (2017) A multicenter study on the diagnostic significance of a single cerebrospinal fluid IgG band. *J*

- Neurol 264:973–978. doi: 10.1007/s00415-017-8480-5
29. Giardina A, Ferrante A, Ciccio F, Vadalà M, Giardina E, Triolo G (2011) One year study of efficacy and safety of infliximab in the treatment of patients with ocular and neurological Behçet's disease refractory to standard immunosuppressive drugs. *Rheumatol Int* 31:33–37. doi: 10.1007/S00296-009-1213-Z
 30. Giza M, Koftori D, Chen L, Bowness P (2018) Is Behçet's disease a "class 1-opathy"? The role of HLA-B*51 in the pathogenesis of Behçet's disease. *Clin Exp Immunol* 191:11–18. doi: 10.1111/CEI.13049
 31. Gönül M, Kılıç A, Gençler B, Gönül M, Kılıç A, Gençler B (2019) The History and Diagnosis of Behçet's Disease. *Different Aspects of Behçet's Disease*. doi: 10.5772/INTECHOPEN.89927
 32. Grayson PC, Yazici Y, Merideth M, Sen HN, Davis M, Novakovich E, Joyal E, Goldbach-Mansky R, Sibley CH (2017) Treatment of mucocutaneous manifestations in Behçet's disease with anakinra: a pilot open-label study. *Arthritis Res Ther* 19. doi: 10.1186/S13075-017-1222-3
 33. Gueudry J, Leclercq M, Saadoun D, Bodaghi B (2021) Old and New Challenges in Uveitis Associated with Behçet's Disease. *J Clin Med* 10. doi: 10.3390/jcm10112318
 34. Gül A (2014) Genetics of Behçet's disease: lessons learned from genomewide association studies. *Curr Opin Rheumatol* 26:56–63. doi: 10.1097/BOR.000000000000003
 35. Haertle M, Kallweit U, Weller M, Linnebank M (2014) The presence of oligoclonal IgG bands in human CSF during the course of neurological diseases. *J Neurol* 261:554–560. doi: 10.1007/s00415-013-7234-2
 36. Hasan MS, Bergmeier LA, Petrushkin H, Fortune F (2015) Gamma Delta ($\gamma\delta$) T Cells and Their Involvement in Behçet's Disease. *J Immunol Res* 2015:705831. doi: 10.1155/2015/705831
 37. Hatemi G, Christensen R, Bang D, Bodaghi B, Celik AF, Fortune F, Gaudric J, Gul A, Kötter I, Leccese P, Mahr A, Moots R, Ozguler Y, Richter J, Saadoun D, Salvarani C, Scuderi F, Sfikakis PP, Siva A, Stanford M, Tugal-Tutkun I, West R, Yurdakul S, Olivieri I, Yazici H (2018) 2018 update of the EULAR recommendations for the management of Behçet's syndrome. *Ann Rheum Dis* 77:808–818. doi: 10.1136/ANNRHEUMDIS-2018-213225
 38. Hirohata S, Kikuchi H, Sawada T, Nagafuchi H, Kuwana M, Takeno M, Ishigatsubo Y (2012) Clinical characteristics of neuro-Behçet's disease in Japan: a multicenter retrospective analysis. *Mod Rheumatol* 22:405–413. doi: 10.1007/S10165-011-0533-5
 39. Hisamatsu T, Ueno F, Matsumoto T, Kobayashi K, Koganei K, Kunisaki R, Hirai F, Nagahori M, Matsushita M, Kobayashi K, Kishimoto M, Takeno M, Tanaka M, Inoue N, Hibi T (2014) The 2nd edition of consensus statements for the diagnosis and management of intestinal Behçet's disease: indication of anti-TNF α monoclonal antibodies. *J Gastroenterol* 49:156–162. doi: 10.1007/S00535-013-0872-4
 40. Hou S, Yang Z, Du L, Jiang Z, Shu Q, Chen Y, Li F, Zhou Q, Ohno S, Chen R, Kijlstra A, Rosenbaum JT, Yang P (2012) Identification of a susceptibility locus in STAT4 for Behçet's disease in Han Chinese in a genome-wide association study. *Arthritis Rheum* 64:4104–4113. doi: 10.1002/ART.37708
 41. Houman MH, Bellakhal S, Salem T Ben, Hamzaoui A, Braham A, Lamoum M, Monia SK, Ghorbel I Ben (2013) Characteristics of neurological manifestations of Behçet's disease: A retrospective monocentric study in Tunisia. *Clin Neurol Neurosurg* 115:2015–2018. doi: 10.1016/j.clineuro.2013.06.009
 42. van der Houwen T, van Laar J (2020) Behçet's Disease, and the Role of TNF- α and TNF- α Blockers. *Int J Mol Sci* 21:3072. doi: 10.3390/IJMS21093072
 43. Huang Y, Yu H, Cao Q, Deng J, Huang X, Kijlstra A, Yang P (2017) The Association of Chemokine Gene Polymorphisms with VKH and Behçet's Disease in a Chinese Han Population. *Biomed Res Int* 2017. doi: 10.1155/2017/1274960

44. Ideguchi H, Suda A, Takeno M, Miyagi R, Ueda A, Ohno S, Ishigatsubo Y (2014) Gastrointestinal manifestations of Behçet's disease in Japan: a study of 43 patients. *Rheumatol Int* 34:851–856. doi: 10.1007/S00296-013-2838-5
45. Jennette JC, Falk RJ, Bacon PA, Basu N, Cid MC, Ferrario F, Flores-Suarez LF, Gross WL, Guillevin L, Hagen EC, Hoffman GS, Jayne DR, Kallenberg CGM, Lamprecht P, Langford CA, Luqmani RA, Mahr AD, Matteson EL, Merkel PA, Ozen S, Pusey CD, Rasmussen N, Rees AJ, Scott DGI, Specks U, Stone JH, Takahashi K, Watts RA (2013) 2012 Revised International Chapel Hill consensus conference nomenclature of vasculitides. *Arthritis Rheum* 65:1–11. doi: 10.1002/ART.37715
46. Le Joncour A, Martos R, Loyau S, Lelay N, Dossier A, Cazes A, Fouret P, Domont F, Papo T, Jandrot-Perrus M, Bouton MC, Cacoub P, Ajzenberg N, Saadoun D, Boulaftali Y (2019) Critical role of neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) in patients with Behçet's disease. *Ann Rheum Dis* 78:1274–1282. doi: 10.1136/ANNRHEUMDIS-2018-214335
47. Kalra S, Silman A, Akman-Demir G, Bohlega S, Borhani-Haghighi A, Constantinescu CS, Houman H, Mahr A, Salvarani C, Sfikakis PP, Siva A, Al-Araji A (2014) Diagnosis and management of Neuro-Behçet's disease: international consensus recommendations. *J Neurol* 261:1662–1676. doi: 10.1007/S00415-013-7209-3
48. Kaneko F, Togashi A, Nomura E, Nakamura K (2014) A New Diagnostic Way for Behçet's Disease: Skin Prick with Self-Saliva. *Genet Res Int* 2014:581468. doi: 10.1155/2014/581468
49. Karadag O, Bolek EC (2020) Management of Behçet's syndrome. *Rheumatology* 59:iii108–iii117. doi: 10.1093/RHEUMATOLOGY/KEAA086
50. Keskin M, Polat G, Ayrancı A, Karadeniz G, Üçsular FD, Büyüksirin M, Yalnız E (2020) Insidious hughes stovin syndrome: Journey from pulmonary embolism to pulmonary arterial aneurysm. *Turk Thorac J* 21:350–353. doi: 10.5152/TurkThoracJ.2018.19088
51. Kidd DP (2017) Neurological complications of Behçet's syndrome. *J Neurol* 264:2178–2183. doi: 10.1007/S00415-017-8436-9
52. Kim DY, Cho S, Choi MJ, Sohn S, Lee E-S, Bang D (2013) Immunopathogenic Role of Herpes Simplex Virus in Behçet's Disease. *Genet Res Int* 2013:638273. doi: 10.1155/2013/638273
53. Kirino Y, Bertias G, Ishigatsubo Y, Mizuki N, Tugal-Tutkun I, Seyahi E, Ozyazgan Y, Sacli FS, Erer B, Inoko H, Emrence Z, Cakar A, Abaci N, Ustek D, Satorius C, Ueda A, Takeno M, Kim Y, Wood GM, Ombrello MJ, Meguro A, Gül A, Remmers EF, Kastner DL (2013) Genome-wide association analysis identifies new susceptibility loci for Behçet's disease and epistasis between HLA-B*51 and ERAP1. *Nat Genet* 45:202–207. doi: 10.1038/NG.2520
54. Kural-Seyahi E, Fresko I, Seyahi N, Ozyazgan Y, Mat C, Hamuryudan V, Yurdakul S, Yazici H (2003) The long-term mortality and morbidity of Behçet syndrome: a 2-decade outcome survey of 387 patients followed at a dedicated center. *Medicine* 82:60–76. doi: 10.1097/00005792-200301000-00006
55. Kutlubay Z, Tüzün Y, Wolf R (2017) The Pathergy Test as a Diagnostic Tool. *SKINmed Dermatology for the Clinician*
56. Leccese P, Alpsoy E (2019) Behçet's disease: An overview of etiopathogenesis. *Front Immunol* 10:426961. doi: 10.3389/FIMMU.2019.01067/BIBTEX
57. Leccese P, Alpsoy E (2019) Behçet's disease: An overview of etiopathogenesis. *Front Immunol* 10
58. Leccese P, Ozguler Y, Christensen R, Esatoglu SN, Bang D, Bodaghi B, Celik AF, Fortune F, Gaudric J, Gül A, Kötter I, Mahr A, Moots RJ, Richter J, Saadoun D, Salvarani C, Scuderi F, Sfikakis PP, Siva A, Stanford M, Tugal-Tutkun I, West R, Yurdakul S, Olivieri I, Yazici H, Hatemi G (2019) Management of skin, mucosa and joint involvement of Behçet's syndrome: A systematic review for update of the EULAR recommendations for the management of Behçet's syndrome. *Semin Arthritis Rheum* 48:752–762. doi:

- 10.1016/J.SEMARTHTRIT.2018.05.008
59. Liu J, Zhao C, Zheng W (2023) Response to: “Correspondence on ‘A pilot study of tofacitinib for refractory Behçet’s syndrome’” by Zou et al. *Ann Rheum Dis* 82:E101. doi: 10.1136/ANNRHEUMDIS-2020-219828
 60. Maggi P, Absinta M, Grammatico M, Vuolo L, Emmi G, Carlucci G, Spagni G, Barilaro A, Repice AM, Emmi L, Prisco D, Martinelli V, Scotti R, Sadeghi N, Perrotta G, Sati P, Dachy B, Reich DS, Filippi M, Massacesi L (2018) Central vein sign differentiates Multiple Sclerosis from central nervous system inflammatory vasculopathies. *Ann Neurol* 83:283–294. doi: 10.1002/ANA.25146
 61. Mahr A, Maldini C (2014) [Epidemiology of Behçet’s disease]. *Rev Med Interne* 35:81–89. doi: 10.1016/J.REVMED.2013.12.005
 62. Maldini C, Lavalley MP, Cheminant M, de menthon M, Mahr A (2012) Relationships of HLA-B51 or B5 genotype with Behçet’s disease clinical characteristics: Systematic review and meta-analyses of observational studies. *Rheumatology* 51:887–900. doi: 10.1093/rheumatology/ker428
 63. McNally TW, Damato EM, Murray PI, Denniston AK, Barry RJ (2017) An update on the use of biologic therapies in the management of uveitis in Behçet’s disease: A comprehensive review. *Orphanet J Rare Dis* 12:1–12. doi: 10.1186/S13023-017-0681-6/TABLES/2
 64. Mease PJ, Hatemi G, Paris M, Cheng S, Maes P, Zhang W, Shi R, Flower A, Picard H, Stein Gold L (2023) Apremilast Long-Term Safety Up to 5 Years from 15 Pooled Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Studies of Psoriasis, Psoriatic Arthritis, and Behçet’s Syndrome. *Am J Clin Dermatol* 24:809–820. doi: 10.1007/S40257-023-00783-7
 65. Mohamed C, Najib K, Essaadouni L (2015) Radiological findings in Behçet disease. *Pan Afr Med J* 20:51. doi: 10.11604/PAMJ.2015.20.51.5928
 66. Mohammadpour M, Kosari M, Khorrami-Nejad M (2019) Behçet’s Disease Presenting With Bilateral Hypopyon Masquerading Post Cataract Surgery Endophthalmitis. *Int Med Case Rep J* 12:363–365. doi: 10.2147/IMCRJ.S232948
 67. Nasr H, Scriven JM (2015) Superficial thrombophlebitis (superficial venous thrombosis). *BMJ (Online)* 350. doi: 10.1136/BMJ.H2039
 68. Nelson CA, Stephen S, Ashchyan HJ, James WD, Micheletti RG, Rosenbach M (2018) Neutrophilic dermatoses: Pathogenesis, Sweet syndrome, neutrophilic eccrine hidradenitis, and Behçet disease. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 79:987–1006. doi: 10.1016/J.JAAD.2017.11.064
 69. Noel N, Drier A, Wechsler B, Piette JC, De Paz R, Dormont D, Cacoub P, Saadoun D (2014) [Neurological manifestations of Behçet’s disease]. *Rev Med Interne* 35:112–120. doi: 10.1016/J.REVMED.2013.10.332
 70. Oguz ID, Hizli P, Gonul M, Oguz ID, Hizli P, Gonul M (2017) The Epidemiology of Behçet’s Disease. *Behçet’s Disease*. doi: 10.5772/68055
 71. Rahman S, Daveluy S (2023) Pathergy Test. *StatPearls*
 72. Saadoun D, Wechsler B, Desseaux K, Le Thi Huong D, Amoura Z, Resche-Rigon M, Cacoub P (2010) Mortality in Behçet’s disease. *Arthritis Rheum* 62:2806–2812. doi: 10.1002/ART.27568
 73. Sabbadini MG, Franchini S (2014) Behçet’s Disease. Differential Diagnosis. *Rare Diseases of the Immune System* 177–188. doi: 10.1007/978-88-470-5477-6_16
 74. Safi R, Kallas R, Bardawil T, Mehanna CJ, Abbas O, Hamam R, Uthman I, Kibbi AG, Nassar D (2018) Neutrophils contribute to vasculitis by increased release of neutrophil extracellular traps in Behçet’s disease. *J Dermatol Sci* 92:143–150. doi: 10.1016/J.JDERMSCI.2018.08.010
 75. Saip S, Akman-Demir G, Siva A (2014) Neuro-Behçet syndrome. *Handb Clin Neurol* 121:1703–1723. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-7020-4088-7.00110-3
 76. Saleh Z, Arayssi T (2014) Update on the therapy of Behçet disease. *Ther Adv Chronic Dis*

- 5:112–134. doi: 10.1177/2040622314523062
77. Salmaninejad A, Gowhari A, Hosseini S, Aslani S, Yousefi M, Bahrami T, Ebrahimi M, Nesaei A, Zal M (2017) Genetics and immunodysfunction underlying Behçet's disease and immunomodulant treatment approaches. *J Immunotoxicol* 14:137–151. doi: 10.1080/1547691X.2017.1346008
 78. Sarr SA, Fall PD, Mboup MC, Dia K, Bodian M, Jobe M (2015) Superior vena cava syndrome revealing a Behçet's disease. *Thromb J* 13. doi: 10.1186/S12959-015-0039-Z
 79. Senusi AA, Mather J, Ola D, Bergmeier LA, Gokani B, Fortune F (2022) The impact of multifactorial factors on the Quality of Life of Behçet's patients over 10 years. *Front Med (Lausanne)* 9:996571. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2022.996571
 80. Sequeira FF, Daryani D (2011) The oral and skin pathergy test. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol* 77:526–530. doi: 10.4103/0378-6323.82399
 81. Seyahi E (2019) Phenotypes in Behçet's syndrome. *Intern Emerg Med* 14:677–689. doi: 10.1007/S11739-019-02046-Y
 82. Skef W, Hamilton MJ, Arayssi T (2015) Gastrointestinal Behçet's disease: A review. *World Journal of Gastroenterology : WJG* 21:3801. doi: 10.3748/WJG.V21.I13.3801
 83. Sulu B, Hatemi G (2024) New and future perspectives in Behçet's syndrome. *Arch Rheumatol* 39:511–521. doi: 10.46497/ARCHRHEUMATOL.2024.11049
 84. Takeuchi M, Ombrello MJ, Kirino Y, Erer B, Tugal-Tutkun I, Seyahi E, Özyazgan Y, Watts NR, Gül A, Kastner DL, Remmers EF (2016) A single endoplasmic reticulum aminopeptidase-1 protein allotype is a strong risk factor for Behçet's disease in HLA-B*51 carriers. *Ann Rheum Dis* 75:2208–2211. doi: 10.1136/ANNRHEUMDIS-2015-209059
 85. Tong B, Liu X, Xiao J, Su G (2019) Immunopathogenesis of Behçet's Disease. *Front Immunol* 10. doi: 10.3389/FIMMU.2019.00665
 86. Tugal-Tutkun I, Gupta V, Cunningham ET (2013) Differential diagnosis of behçet uveitis. *Ocul Immunol Inflamm* 21:337–350. doi: 10.3109/09273948.2013.795228
 87. Vitale A, Emmi G, Lopalco G, Fabiani C, Gentileschi S, Silvestri E, Di Scala G, Iannone F, Frediani B, Galeazzi M, Lapadula G, Rigante D, Cantarini L (2019) Correction to: Long-term efficacy and safety of golimumab in the treatment of multirefractory Behçet's disease. *Clin Rheumatol* 38:267. doi: 10.1007/S10067-018-4302-0
 88. Vitale A, Rigante D, Caso F, Brizi MG, Galeazzi M, Costa L, Franceschini R, Lucherini OM, Cantarini L (2014) Inhibition of interleukin-1 by canakinumab as a successful mono-drug strategy for the treatment of refractory Behçet's disease: a case series. *Dermatology* 228:211–214. doi: 10.1159/000358125
 89. Volle G, Fraison JB, Gobert D, Goulenok T, Dhote R, Fain O, Gonzalez-Chiappe S, Lhote F, Papo T, Thuillier A, Rivière S, Mahr A (2017) Dietary and Nondietary Triggers of Oral Ulcer Recurrences in Behçet's Disease. *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken)* 69:1429–1436. doi: 10.1002/ACR.23155
 90. Yazici H, Seyahi E, Hatemi G, Yazici Y (2018) Behçet syndrome: a contemporary view. *Nat Rev Rheumatol* 14:107–119. doi: 10.1038/NRRHEUM.2017.208
 91. Yazici H, Ugurlu S, Seyahi E (2012) Behçet syndrome: is it one condition? *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol* 43:275–280. doi: 10.1007/S12016-012-8319-X
 92. Yu HH, Chiang BL (2023) Genital ulcers in acute Epstein-Barr virus infection mimicking Behçet's disease. *Clin Rheumatol* 42:633–634. doi: 10.1007/S10067-022-06447-X/FIGURES/1
 93. Zając H, Turno-Kręcicka A (2021) Ocular Manifestations of Behçet's Disease: An Update on Diagnostic Challenges and Disease Management. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 2021, Vol 10, Page 5174 10:5174. doi: 10.3390/JCM10215174
 94. (PDF) One year in review 2020: Behçet's syndrome. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348363201_One_year_in_review_2020_Behcet's_syndrome](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348363201_One_year_in_review_2020_Behcet_s_syndrome). Accessed 31 Jan 2025

95. Global distribution of Behçet's disease [14]. | Download Scientific Diagram. https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Figure-1-Global-distribution-of-Behcets-disease-14_fig1_344332652. Accessed 31 Jan 2025
96. (PDF) The prevalence of Behçet's disease in the north of Jordan: a hospital-based epidemiological survey. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321754198_The_prevalence_of_Behcet's_disease_in_the_north_of_Jordan_a_hospital-based_epidemiological_survey. Accessed 31 Jan 2025
97. Potential Infectious Etiology of Behçet's Disease - PMC. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3255303/>. Accessed 22 Jan 2025
98. Natural killer cells dominate a Th-1 polarized response in Behçet's disease patients with uveitis - PubMed. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25937098/>. Accessed 22 Jan 2025
99. (PDF) Exacerbation of Behçet's syndrome and familial Mediterranean fever with menstruation. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321149743_Exacerbation_of_Behcet's_syndrome_and_familial_Mediterranean_fever_with_menstruation. Accessed 16 Jan 2025
100. Oral ulcers in patients with Behçet's disease: (A) A centimetric... | Download Scientific Diagram. https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Oral-ulcers-in-patients-with-Behcets-disease-A-A-centimetric-aphthous-lesion-on-the_fig1_329920014. Accessed 31 Jan 2025
101. Behçet's Disease: A Multifaceted Affliction | Journal of Clinical and Pharmaceutical Research. <https://www.jcpr.in/index.php/journal/article/view/32>. Accessed 16 Jan 2025
102. Gastrointestinal Behçet's disease: A review - PMC. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4385527/>. Accessed 20 Jan 2025
103. How is Behçet's diagnosed? <https://behcetsuk.org/how-is-behcets-diagnosed/>. Accessed 7 Feb 2025
104. Grading and definitions of skin pathology test | Download Table. https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Grading-and-definitions-of-skin-pathology-test_tbl1_14947906. Accessed 12 Feb 2025
105. Differential diagnosis of Behçet's ulcerations. | Download Table. https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Differential-diagnosis-of-Behcets-ulcerations_tbl1_258382117. Accessed 12 Feb 2025
106. Behçet Disease Differential Diagnoses. <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/329099-differential>. Accessed 12 Feb 2025

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**BEHCETS DISEASE - CONTEMPORARY ETIOPATHOGENETIC EXPLANATIONS,
CURRENT DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT POSSIBILITIES.**

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Behçet's disease (BD) to be a complicated inflammatory disorder which affects multiple body systems at the same time but lacks clear causes. Its chronic and relapsing nature, significant progress has been made in understanding its pathogenesis and developing effective treatments. This review aims to bridge the gap between current scientific knowledge and clinical practice by examining the latest etiopathogenic explanations, diagnostic approaches, and therapeutic possibilities for BD.

The primary goal of this review is to provide a very deep overview of the contemporary understanding of Behçet's disease. It seeks to integrate new findings on genetic predispositions, environmental triggers such as infections (e.g., *Streptococcus sanguinis*), immune dysregulation involving Th17 cells and regulatory T cells (Tregs), and novel therapeutic strategies including biologics targeting interleukins.

Behçet's disease is characterized by mucocutaneous lesions, ocular involvement, vasculitis, and other systemic manifestations. The pathogenesis involves both innate and adaptive immune responses with key roles played by cytokines like IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α . Genetic factors such as HLA-B51 are strongly associated with BD susceptibility but do not solely determine the disease onset; environmental factors also play crucial roles. Recent advances in treatment include corticosteroids as first-line therapy for acute symptoms alongside newer biologic agents like TNF-alpha antagonists that offer promising outcomes in managing inflammation.

This review highlights the importance of integrating cutting-edge research into clinical practice for improving patient clinical outcomes in Behçet's disease. By synthesizing current knowledge on etiopathogenesis with emerging therapeutic strategies, healthcare providers can develop more effective management plans tailored to individual patient needs. Ultimately, this work contributes significantly to advancing our understanding of BD while guiding future research directions aimed at enhancing diagnosis accuracy and treatment efficacy in this challenging autoimmune condition.